

D1.4 Report Year 1 on Dissemination and Communication

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www.dihnet.eu

About the DIHNET.EU project

The overall aim of DIHNET.EU is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

The project is carried out by TNO, Tecnalia, Fundingbox, euRobotics, BluMorpho and FEDIL, have strong experience in DIHs and well connected to the EU DIH community.

Executive Summary

In the first year of the project, dissemination work has focused initially on creating the project website www.dihnet.eu and the [DIHNET.EU community platform](#). A number of articles from project partners and the DIHNET community, together with participation in conferences and workshops and the co-organisation of the 7th working group meeting, raised the profile of the project. This resulted in at least 13 articles on DIHNET appearing in online media.

Dissemination and coordination within the Digital Innovation Hubs networks included the Champions Challenge, webinars on community building and Internet of Things (IoT), and the DIHNET working groups. Links have been established with the DIH networks projects [AI-DIH](#) and [RODIN](#) to organise joint workshops on cost and benefits of cooperation and business models and sustainability, respectively.

In order to reach a wider audience, we also utilized online social media Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn. The DIHNET community platform has been welcomed by the Digital Innovation Hubs community with a good number of 331 registrations and a high level of user's engagement in the webinars and DIHNET working groups.

Building a community is a process that takes time and effort over a period of several years. The first stones for building the DIHNET community have been well set in Year 1; and strategic efforts to nurture the community will be put in place to make sure it keeps growing during the second year of the project.

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1 Introduction

The DIHNET.EU project enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The project aims at creating a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

This deliverable contains first, information on the communication and dissemination activities organised and attended by the DIHNET consortium partners following the information required in the project continuous reporting; and second, an analysis and evaluation of DIHNET's website, community platform, and press and social media coverage during Year 1: November 2018 – October 2019.

2 Publications

The project publications are classified in two categories: academic publications and non-scientific or non-peer reviewed publications. In Year 1, the consortium partners published only in the non-scientific category. Due to the nature of the project being a coordination Support Action (CSA), we expect a low number of academic publications during the project lifetime, as it is not a principal aim of the project to produce such publications. However, we expect to have academic publications in the future.

2.1 Academic publications

The project does not have academic publications in this first year. We expect this type of publications at the end of the project, when information has been gathered and analysed, and the results are published.

2.2 Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publication (popularised publication)

Various members of the DIHNET consortium have published in specialist platforms seeking to reach the DIHs community. TNO and BLUMORPHO (BM) have contributed to the DIHNET community by publishing two articles on DIHs and digitisation. euRobotics (ER) has contributed to an article on Digital Innovation Hubs and DIH networks published on Robohub.org, a well-regarded¹ robotics portal with international coverage. TECNALIA has also contributed with four articles: two on working groups and DIHNET were published in the JRC website and two on the catalogue and the champions challenge were published on the DIHNET community.

Author	Date	Title	Link
Begoña Sánchez (TECNALIA)	23/04/2019	Join the DIHNET Community	https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/-/launch-of-the-dihnet-eu-community?inheritRedirect=true
Begoña Sánchez (TECNALIA)	27/04/2019	Guidelines to prepare candidature to be part of the Catalogue	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-community-dihnet-eu-criteria-to-be-part-of-dihs-catalogue
Begoña Sánchez (TECNALIA)	12/05/2019	Are you a DIH? Register now to the Working Group of your interest of the DIHNET.EU	https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/-/are-you-a-dih-register-now-to-the-working-group-of-your-interest-of-the-dihnet-eu-community?inheritRedirect=true
Maurits Butter (TNO)	13/05/2019	EU collaboration is not obvious for individual DIHs. But it can be!	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-community-dihnet-eu-introduce-yourself-1/5cd994e4a25b0f0864d63c78
Begoña Sánchez (TECNALIA)	27/07/2019	The DIHs Champions Challenge 2019 is now launched	https://fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-community-dihnet-eu-news-events/5d25d861edf1910864ab6f3b

¹ <https://robohub.org/robohub-is-a-top-10-brand-in-robotics/>

Sabine Hauert from Robohub.org with contributions from Lavinia Cinca and Reinhard Lafrenz (ER)	02/09/2019	Encouraging robot uptake through Europe's network of Digital Innovation Hubs	https://robohub.org/encouraging-robot-uptake-through-europes-network-of-digital-innovation-hubs/
Olivia Uguen (BM)	04/09/2019	Digitising European Industry: shaping the European companies' digital transformation thanks to a strong Digital Innovation Hubs' network!	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-community-dihnet-eu-news-events/5d6f72329d14ce615181bf6d

3 Dissemination

In the context of dissemination within Horizon 2020 projects, we aim at sharing the project results with potential users in the research field, industry and policymakers. We expect that by sharing the results with the rest of the Digital Innovation Hubs community, we contribute to the progress of science and digitisation in general.

The DIHNET consortium partners have promoted the project and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (i.e policy makers, DIH networks, SMEs and general public), in an effective manner. In this section we list the different events organised and the channels used to communicate the information.

3.1 Conferences

In Year 1, we co-organised with the European Commission the Seventh meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs and a side event during the Digital Enterprise Show 2019 in Madrid.

- **Digital Enterprise Show 2019, Madrid, Spain. 23th May 2019**

The DIHNET consortium was invited to organise a side event during the Digital Enterprise Show 2019 in Madrid (21-23 of May 2019). This large international event hosted around 25,000 participants who gather every year in Madrid to discuss how the digital changes the business, to acquire the crucial knowledge, skills and solutions to shape their industries' future. During this event, the DIHNET consortium facilitated discussions on European collaboration during a 3.50 hrs workshop. Mayte Carracedo (FBA) was invited speaker: "The role of Regions supporting DIHs cross-border collaboration". Maurits Butter (TNO) introduced and moderated two sessions at the DES 2019: "Digital Innovation Hub Workshop – Part 1" and "Digital Innovation Hub Workshop – Part 2 – Panel discussion 1: Pan-EU collaborations; challenging but beneficial". Begoña Sánchez (TECNALICA) was also present at this event as speaker in the "Panel discussion 2: Creating a European DIH Community:DIH Catalogue instrumental to create a Community".

<http://www.des-madrid.com/>

The estimated number of people reached is **10** from **Scientific community**, **10** from **Industry**, **30** from **Civil Society**, **10** from the **general public** and **10** from **Policy Makers**.

- **Seventh meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs, Brussels, Belgium. 1st July 2019**

Mayte Carracedo (FBA), Ruud Baartmans (TNO), and Begoña Sánchez (TECNALIA) presented during the event. In this event we presented the DIHNET project network and announced the DIH Champion Challenge during the proceedings of the DEI Working Group meeting.

DIHNET Working Group meetings were also organised, several discussions run in parallel and the summaries were shared with the audience.

The 7th WG meeting group was also attended by Olivia Uguen (BM), Kristina Karanikolova (TNO) Reinhard Lafrenz (ER), Marta Palau (ER) and Maria Roca (FBA).

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/seventh-meeting-working-group-digital-innovation-hubs>

This event hosted by the European Commission and co-organised by the DIHNET.EU project, took place on the 1st of July 2019 in Brussels. More than 200 stakeholders from Member States, regions, industry, research institutions and universities, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), networks, and clusters attended the meeting to discuss how existing DIHs and the upcoming European

Digital Innovation Hubs will contribute to support and build a digital future that benefits European businesses and society.

During paralleled sessions, each of the DIHNET working groups (WG) from the DIHNET community held physical workshops on their respective challenges and future work:

- WG1 Funding & finance (FBA): Exploration of new funding sources to establish cooperation among DIHs and to facilitate the uptake of digital innovations by SMEs.
- WG2 Collaboration (ER): Effective and sustainable collaboration at all levels (internal, regional, national and EU-wide) with special attention to cross-border collaboration and tools.
- WG3 National and regional policies (TECNALIA): Coherent and continuous connection to the regional, national policies and strategies to digitalise industry.
- WG4 Business models & sustainability (BM): Business models for DIHs (how to structure services, possible legal forms, partners recruiting, etc) and how to reach sustainability.

Each WG leader led the discussions together with a designated reporter to share the results during the plenary conference.

Figure 1: 7 WG meeting on DIHs (Photo Credits: DIHNET/euRobotics)

This event was attended by **approx. 200 people**, although we do not know the numbers associated to each of the categories of audience.

3.2 Workshops

DIHNET's partner Funding Box (FBA) has organised two webinars addressed mainly targeting the Industry community and SMEs as part of Funding Box work in WP2-Task 2.2. These webinars are available on the DIHNET.EU community platform.

- **DIHNET.EU webinar: community building, online webinar.** 23rd May 2019.
Andrés Sanchez (FBA), WP2 – Task 2.2

Figure 2: DIHNET webinar on Community building (Source: Funding Box)

DIHs should be able to communicate about the help that can be offered to the potential end users. We believe that this communication can be leveraged by the network effect that a community or ecosystem may bring. That was exactly the topic that Andres Sanchez -@andres.ss - addressed during DIHNET webinar on community building that was held online on past 28th May. He explained that community building should go through three different phases: mapping, attraction and activation. <https://fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-community-dihnet-eu-news-events/5cf6b9b1a25b0f0864d643e6>

The estimated number of people reached is **39** people from **Industry**.

- **IoT network of Digital Innovation Hubs, online webinar.** 11th September 2019.
María Roca (FBA) organised the workshop. The speaker was Pierre-Yves Danet from AIOTI.
WP2 – Task 2.2

Figure 3: DIHNET webinar on AOITI (Source: Funding Box)

The missions of the AIOTI network will be to support the growth of the community of IoT DIHs and to build local communities in which the role of relevant technologies would be developed, boosted and consolidated. Currently the network is composed of 10 DIHs, and an Open Call will

be launched to expand the network and involve more DIHs. Finally, he presented the parts of the Digital Europe program in Horizon Europe which offer EC funding for DIH networks.

<https://fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-community-dihnet-eu-news-events/5d84af4152317832f858fae5>

The estimated number of people reached is **28** people from **Industry**.

- TECNALIA, in cooperation with each partner in charge of the DIHNET working groups: BLUMORPHO (BM), euRobotics (ER) and Funding Box (FBA), organised 4 webinars of the working groups in the community platform. The aim of those webinars was to present the challenges that the participants of each Working Group should address during the whole duration of the project and to explain how the work should be organised. The four webinars meeting took place on 19th June 2019. The webinars gathered in average about **30** people for each **Working Group**.

3.3 Press releases

euRobotics with contributions from FBA, TNO, TECNALIA and the European Commission, wrote a press release about the 7th Working Group meeting on DIHs.

Author	Date	Title	Link
Marta Palau Franco (ER) with contributions from Maria Roca (FBA), Kristina Karanikolova (TNO), Reinhard Lafrenz (ER), Ruud Bartmans (TNO), Begoña Sanchez (TECNALIA) and Andrea Halmos (EC)	16/07/2019	Seventh meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs: the key role of DIHs in a digitised Europe	https://www.eu-robotics.net/eurobotics/newsroom/press/seventh-meeting-of-the-working-group-on-dihs.html

3.4 Local Press conferences / Media Briefings

No local press conference or media briefing has taken place in this first year. Due to the nature of this Coordination and Support Action (CSA), we do not expect to organise this type of dissemination events.

3.5 Training

DIHNET Q&A session in May on the JRC Catalogue organised by Tecnalía and FBA. Due to the numerous questions received about how to fill the DIH profile of the JRC catalogue of Hubs, DIHNET consortium decided to organise a **Q&A session on Friday 3rd May 2019** to give the opportunity to hubs to get answers to some of their doubts on this regard. Guidelines on how to fill in the

Catalogue DIH applications are available at the DIHNET Community platform. Questions were attended by Begoña Sánchez and Ezekiel Arrizabalaga from TECNALIA and Maria Roca from FBA.

The estimated number of participants was **20** people, although we do not know the numbers associated to each of the categories of audience.

3.6 Participation

Various members of the consortium have disseminated DIHNET network at specialist conferences and events, seeking to reach DIHNET's specific target groups: research community, industry, policy makers and civil society.

The conferences, workshops and other events partners have participated in are listed in this section.

3.6.1 Conference

In Year1, consortium partners have attended several conferences to present the project:

- **Digital Innovation Hubs Annual Event 2018, Warsaw, Poland.** 28th November 2018
Maurits Butter (TNO) participated at the panel discussion on “Digital Innovation Hubs as brokers in cross-border collaboration”.
Mayte Carracedo (FBA) presented in the session “Success stories from supported SMEs”
<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/digital-innovation-hubs-annual-event-presentations-and-highlights>

The Digital Innovation Hubs Annual event hosted more than 300 stakeholders. The main topic of the event was the future of Digital Innovation Hubs in Europe. The two-day event was attended by DIHs, policy makers and technology organizations from around Europe. During the event Maurits Butter participated in a panel discussion and announced the start of the DIHNET project.

This event was attended by approx. **300** people, although we do not know the numbers associated to each of the categories of audience.

- **Fifth meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs, Brussels, Belgium.** 7th November 2018
Maurits Butter (TNO) was an invited speaker, presenting “Post-project sustainability of pan-European Collaboration Networks” as part of Session 3: Measuring the impact of the (Big Data) Digital Innovation Hub.
<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/presentations-fifth-meeting-working-group-digital-innovation-hubs-big-data-and-artificial>

The fifth meeting of the working group focused on the role of DIHs in supporting the uptake of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Europe. Maurits Butter presented the new DIHNET.EU project and its ambitions. Emphasis was on the benefits of pan-EU collaboration and identifying the different players in the current landscape.

The estimated number of people reached is **40** from **Scientific community**, **5** from **Industry**, **5** from **Civil Society** and **10** from **Policy Makers**.

- **Sixth meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs, Brussels, Belgium.** 3rd April 2019.

Begoña Sanchez (TECNALIA) and Maria Roca and Mayte Carracedo (FBA) presented the DIHNET.EU activities within the JRC catalogue and the DIHNET.EU online community was launched.

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/sixth-meeting-working-group-digital-innovation-hubs>

The sixth meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs addressed two topics: (i) Bridging the results of European projects on Digital Innovation Hubs with demand of these services by other DIHs and regions and (ii) Filling the white spots through upcoming H2020 calls and mechanisms for regions to invest in DIHs. During this event Begoña Sanchez and Maria Roca presented the DIH Catalogue & Community platform was launched. Maurits Butter (TNO) presented DIHNET.EU activities and logic regarding smart specialization strategies and their connection to DIHs. The session was titled “DIHNET.EU Pan European collaboration for regional DIHs” and was part of the overall discussions on good practices of collaboration between regions and DIHs

DIHNET.EU COMMUNITY: WHAT CAN YOU FIND?

- 1. Articles & Announcements**
Screenshot of a tweet: "DIHNET.EU, is now in charge of managing the Catalogue and assessing the new and updated DIH applications." The tweet includes a graphic with four sad faces and one happy face.
- 2. Events**
Screenshot of a tweet for "Digital Day 2019" featuring a background of binary code.
- 3. Matchmaking**
Screenshot of a user profile for Maria Roca, showing her bio and contact information.
- 4. Q&A**
Screenshot of a tweet asking for impact numbers from DIHs: "Hi Maria, I would love to see real (or third-party certified) impact numbers from the hubs. The S3 platform currently has uncorrected, self-reported data and it is difficult to see if the information reported is valid or not." The tweet includes a link to a report.

TNO

Figure 4: DIHNET community launch (Source: Funding Box)

The estimated number of people reached is **60** from **Scientific community**, **10** from **Industry**, **20** from **Civil Society** and **20** from **Policy Makers**.

- **Digital Innovation Hubs Day, Stuttgart, Germany. 14th May 2019**
Mayte Carracedo (FBA) was invited speaker. “SAE and I4MS Initiatives; DIHNET.EU”
<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/digital-innovation-hubs-day>
The event brought together key players from neighbouring regions and countries to discuss Digital Innovation Hubs. Participants learned about the different DIHs and initiatives, share their experiences and explore possible collaborations.

Figure 5: Mayte Carracedo at the Digital Innovation Hubs Day (Source: Funding Box)

We do not have the number of attendants for this event.

- **360 Possibles Grand Est, Strasbourg, France. 27th June 2019.**

María Roca (FBA) was invited speaker. "Digital Innovation Hub: Europe at the service of your digital transformation!"

<https://www.360possiblesgrandest.fr/en/home-one-2/>

360 Possibles Grand Est is a collaborative event supported by the innovation stakeholders, is dedicated to companies in order to accelerate their transitions, understand current changes and their impacts on organisations, explore technologies and meet innovators, and access new methods of innovation.

Figure 6: Maria Roca at 360 Possibles Grand Est (Photo credits: Funding Box)

The estimated number of people reached is **10** from **Scientific community**, **10** from **Industry**, **20** from **Civil Society** and **10** from **Policy Makers**.

- **Future Approaches and Recommendations to Enhance Digital Transformation of SMEs, Brussels, Belgium.** 25 June 2019

Maurits Butter (TNO) was an invited speaker presenting “DIHNET: some early observations”
https://smartanythingeverywhere.eu/ec_recommendations/#toggle-id-4

The event was organised by Smart4Europe as an EC consultation meeting on “Future Approaches and Recommendations to Enhance Digital Transformation of SMEs”. The meeting aimed to share the draft recommendations of the Smart4Europe CSA on the topic of collaboration and linking DIHs. Maurits Butter presented observations on the role of IAs in developing links and their connection to DIHs.

We do not have the number of attendants to this event.

- **ICT Proposers’ Day, Helsinki, Finland.** 20th September 2019
 Mayte Carracedo (FBA) as rapporteur. “SO5 Session: Digital Innovation Hubs”. Begoña Sánchez also attended this meeting.
<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/digital-excellence-forum-ict-proposers-day-2019>

Participation in the DIH Panel Discussion in which the Commission presented its plans for implementing the Digital Europe Programme for Digital Innovation Hubs’ capacity building.

Figure 7: ICT Proposers’ Day Helsinki (Photo Credits: Funding Box)

The estimated number of people reached is **60** from **Scientific community**, **10** from **Industry**, **20** from **Civil Society** and **20** from **Policy Makers**.

- **European Week of Cities and Regions, Brussels, Belgium.** 8 October 2019
The European Week of Cities and Regions is an annual event where cities and regions discuss the progress of their territories, the significance of cities and regions to the development of the EU and the cohesion policy of the EU. The session on DIHs and Smart Specialization strategies will explore the interaction of DIHs and regions and the role of DIHs in forming and implementing smart specialization strategies. The challenges of the smart specialization strategies in the area of digitization will also be discussed. Maurits Butter (TNO) was invited speaker at the session on “Digital Innovation Hubs and Smart Specialisation for digital transformation”
https://europa.eu/regions-and-cities/programme/sessions/368_en

The estimated number of people reached is **10** from **Scientific community**, **15** from **Civil Society** and **20** from **Policy Makers**.

3.6.2 Other events

- **Smart Business Festival, Bratislava, Slovakia.** 24th September 2019
María Roca (FBA) was invited speaker. “Opportunities for DIHs offered by the DIHNET.EU project”
<http://smartbusinessfestival.sk/>

The Smart Business Festival is a networking event aimed at promoting innovative business projects, tools and technologies.

The estimated number of people reached is **10** from **Scientific community**, **10** from **Industry**, **5** from **Civil Society**, **5** from **Policy Makers** and **1** from **Media**.

- **10th October 2019. VI ASAMBLEA GENERAL DE PLANETIC, Palma de Mallorca.** Begoña Sánchez, TECNALIA and Mayte Carracedo FBA, were speakers in this conference represented by most of the Spanish DIHs. DIHNET project as well as the JRC Catalogue were presented.
<https://planetec.es/content/jornada-digital-innovation-hubs-dih-vi-asamblea-general>.

The estimated number of people attending this event was **50** people, although we do not know the numbers associated to each of the categories of audience.

3.7 Video/Film

In this first year, the project consortium has not produced any videos or films. It's out of the scope of the project to produce this type of dissemination materials.

3.8 Activities organised jointly with other EU projects

In this first year, we have organised two activities jointly with other EU projects: AI-DIH network project and RODIN network project.

- **Workshop on cost and benefits of cooperation- TP4, Brussels (Belgium).** 3 July 2019
Kristina Karanikolova (TNO) attended the [AI-DIH Network project](#) workshop on cost and benefits for cooperation. Kristina presented the DIHNET project to a group of 30 DIHs across Europe, aiming to develop a network. The presentation focused on pan-European collaboration and shared ideas on possible business models for collaboration developed by the DIHNET project consortium. https://www.ai-dih-network.eu/media_and_training.html#

The estimated number of people reached is **2** from **Scientific community**, **1** from **Industry** and **27** from DIHs categorised under **Other**.

- **Workshop on business models and sustainability - RODIN Summer camp – Delft (Netherlands) - 2nd October 2019**
Olivia Uguen (BM) attended the summer camp of the [RODIN network project](#) to take part to the discussion related to the possible business models that could help the setting-up of sustainable DIHs network for robotics.

The number of people reached is **22** from **Scientific community**, and **6** from **Industry**.

3.9 Public engagement and outreach events

There are not public engagement or outreach events addressed to the general public to report in this Year 1.

3.10 Communication Campaign

This section describes the dissemination through social media and on-line media. Section 3.10.1 includes the analysis of DIHNET's social media channels (i.e. Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn). A detailed compilation of online media articles (published by external sources and not by DIHNET consortium members) is given in Annex 1 of this report, analysed by country, media type, and genre. A total of 13 articles are listed, although this is suspected to be an underestimate, since we are not always advised when items appear; the very nature of present-day communications, particularly over the Internet, makes it impossible to achieve full completeness, as news items go viral and escape our compilation efforts.

We have not organised specific communication campaigns to be present on TV, radio or print media such as newspapers or magazines. Due to the budget limitations, it is out of the scope of the project to pay to be present in those media channels. However, we do not discard the possibility of participation of consortium members in those channels (by invitation) during the lifetime of the project. In Year 1 there are no activities to report concerning television, radio or print media.

3.10.1 Social Media

In order to maximise the reach of DIHNET to a wide range of audiences, we are making use of social media including Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. As expected, social media activities peaked around the 7th Working Group meeting on Digital Innovation Hubs, the survey on DIH sustainability, the DIH champions challenge, the DIHNET community platform, the article on SMEs & eIDAS and the open calls of some innovation actions.

- **Twitter**

The DIHNET Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/DihnetE>) was created in April 2019, although the account was not active posting content until the 1st of July 2019. Since then, the channel has reached a total of **174 followers** and has posted 180 new Tweets (this number includes re-tweets) (as per October 14, 2019), see Figure 8.

Figure 8: Twitter page for DIHNET (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 14, 2019])

The twitter followers have increased since April 2019 and in the last 30 days we have gained around 1 new follower per day, as shown in the twitter analytics in Figure 9 below.

We expect an increase in the number of followers in the next months as more events will be organised and more results will be communicated to our targeted audience.

Figure 9: DIHNET Twitter audience grow in the past 30 days (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 14, 2019])

Over the period of 1 July 2019 – 14 October 2019 the twitter account had a total of **64.000 Impressions** (57.200 + 6.800 impressions) as shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

The tweet activity peaked in July with the 7th Working Group on DIH event and the Survey on DIH sustainability, the champions challenge and the article on the 7th Working Group meeting event. The other peak was in August with the DIHNET community and the article on SMEs & eIDAS published on the DIHNET community. The higher peak was in September on the topic of the final reminders for the registration to the first DIH Champions Challenge. This is show in Figure 12. The twitter activity in October peaked during the DIHNET’s coordinator participation in RODIN network Summer Camp on 1-2 October (see Figure 11 and Figure 13).

Figure 10: Tweet activity DIHNET period 1 Jul 2019 – 29 Sept 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 14, 2019])

Figure 11: DIHNET Tweet activity period 30 Sept 2019 – 14 Oct 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 14, 2019])

The **engagement rate** of the top tweets (see Figure 12 and Figure 13) is **very high**² bearing in mind that we are still building our twitter audience and we only have 174 followers.

² <https://embertelelevision.co.uk/blog/the-beginners-guide-to-twitter-analytics/>

DIHNET.EU @DihnetE · Aug 27 Why Small and Medium enterprises should care about electronic Identification (eID), Authentication and Trust Services #eIDAS? Read the article by EC Policy Officer Alma Joy #Ridderhof on DIHNET community, tinyurl.com/yxlr6kut @eID_EU @eGov_EU @FundingBox @eu_Robotics #SMEs pic.twitter.com/fywAdD2emX View Tweet activity	1,076	15	1.4%
DIHNET.EU @DihnetE · Aug 27 Join the DIHNET Community, the on-line platform for #DIHs ! Discuss topics on #DigitalInnovation, be part of working groups, exchange ideas and network with other colleagues. dihnet-community-1.fundingbox.com #H2020 @eu_Robotics @EU_DIHELP @RODIN_network @FundingBox @DSMeu pic.twitter.com/8WrEHWH7X0 View Tweet activity	1,361	24	1.8%
DIHNET.EU @DihnetE · Jul 1 Rudd Baartmans from #TNO and the DIHNET.EU coordination and support action introduces the project and the agenda for the 7th Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs #DIHs pic.twitter.com/bJIGRIeFcw View Tweet activity	1,751	12	0.7%

Figure 12: DIHNET Top tweets period 1 July 2019 – 29 Sept 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 14, 2019])

Figure 13: DIHNET Top tweets period 30 Sept 2019 – 14 Oct 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 14, 2019])

The **twitter audience** interests are in line with our brand and targeted audience as top interests include **Science news, Technology and Tech news.** (see Figure 14)

Figure 14: DIHNET Facebook page (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

- **Facebook**

The DIHNET Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/>) started its activity on the 1st of July 2019, reaching a total of 23 people likes and 28 people follows as of October 14, 2019, as shown in Figure 15 and Figure 16.

Figure 15: DIHNET Facebook page (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

Figure 16: DIHNET Facebook Daily New Likes (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

Facebook activity peaked around the Survey on DIH sustainability, the registration for the first DIH champions challenge, and the open calls of the innovation actions DIH2, DIH-HERO and L4Ms, as shown in Figure 17 and Figure 21.

Figure 17: DIHNET Facebook Daily Total Impressions (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

During the period of 1 July 2019 to 14th October 2019, we had a total of **5167 daily impressions**. euRobotics has not done any paid promoted content in this first year, so the daily organic impressions chart (see Figure 18) is almost the same as the Daily total impressions (see Figure 17).

Figure 18: DIHNET Facebook Daily Organic Impressions Daily (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

The total daily reach of unique users from 1 July 2019 to 14 October 2019 is **3348 people**, as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: DIHNET Facebook Daily Reach of Page Posts (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

Individual reach and engagement of some of the posts is shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22 below. The publications with a high engagement have been those related with the innovation actions or DIH networks calls (Trinity, L4Ms, DIH2, DIH-HERO), the Champions challenge and the survey on DIHs. The overall engagement rate is quite good bearing in mind the number of followers, but more work needs to be done to increase the number of followers. This may include paying promotion advertise linked to specific DIHNET events or publication of results with the aim to reach a wider audience. However, looking at the rate of new followers despite the engagement, maybe the Facebook platform is not the best suited for targeting DIHNET specialist audience.

is **Insights** Publishing Tools Ad Centre More ▾ Edit Page Info Settings Help

Reach: Organic/Paid Post clicks Reactions, comments & shares

Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement	Promote
01/10/2019 15:56		11	1 1	Boost Post		
23/09/2019 10:30		11	1 0	Boost Post		
19/09/2019 11:15		12	0 0	Boost Post		
18/09/2019 10:30		9	0 0	Boost Post		
13/09/2019 08:28		8	0 0	Boost Post		
07/09/2019 12:00		10	1 1	Boost Post		
06/09/2019 09:20		10	0 0	Boost Post		
03/09/2019 10:32		14	1 0	Boost Post		
02/09/2019 15:50		11	0 0	Boost Post		
28/08/2019 11:00		8	0 0	Boost Post		
27/08/2019 20:06		9	0 1	Boost Post		
26/08/2019 14:55		11	1 0	Boost Post		
26/08/2019 09:03		9	1 1	Boost Post		

Figure 20: Post reach for DIHNET's Facebook page (Part 1 of 2) (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

21/08/2019 16:05		Boost Post						
20/08/2019 16:05		Boost Post						
19/08/2019 15:30		Boost Post						
16/08/2019 14:00		Boost Post						
13/08/2019 08:58		Boost Post						
12/08/2019 10:37		Boost Post						
12/08/2019 10:30		Boost Post						
07/08/2019 14:05		Boost Post						
02/08/2019 10:45		Boost Post						
01/08/2019 16:15		Boost Post						
01/08/2019 11:30		Boost Post						
31/07/2019 11:00		Boost Post						
30/07/2019 10:19		Boost Post						
18/07/2019 09:55		Boost Post						
17/07/2019 09:34		Boost Post						
15/07/2019 11:39		Boost Post						
11/07/2019 11:38		Boost Post						
11/07/2019 10:47		Boost Post						

Figure 21: Post reach for DIHNET's Facebook page (Part 2 of 2) (Source: <https://www.facebook.com/dihnet/> [Accessed October 14, 2019])

- **LinkedIn**

The LinkedIn page for DIHNET (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/dihneteu>) was created in April 2019 and started posting information on 31 July 2019. The page currently has 19 followers (see Figure 22 and Figure 23) a number that we expect to increase in the next months when we disseminate more content. All this as per October 13, 2019.

Figure 22: DIHNET LinkedIn page header (Source: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/dihneteu> [Accessed October 16, 2019])

Figure 23: DIHNET LinkedIn follower metrics period 31 Mar 2019 – 15 Oct 2019 (Source: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/dihneteu> [Accessed October 16, 2019])

The number of impressions and unique impressions have peaked around the month of August as show in Figure 24 and Figure 25. The publications with more impressions and higher reach (see Figure 26) were about Trinity DIH network open calls, the Cybersecurity conference for Robotics 2019 linked to Trinity open calls, and the 7th Working Group meeting on DIHs. The impressions have decreased after August due to less content being published on the page.

Figure 24: DIHNET LinkedIn Impressions period 31 March 2019 – 13 Oct 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 13, 2019])

Figure 25: DIHNET LinkedIn Unique Impressions period 31 March 2019 – 13 Oct 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 13, 2019])

Update engagement Show: 20

Update title	Posted by	Created	Impressions	Video views	Clicks	CTR	Reactions	Comments	Shares	Follow
Programming Scheme All followers	Marta Palau...	10/23/2019	4	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
Programming Scheme - Czechinno All followers	Marta Palau...	10/21/2019	10	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
Tomorrow is the last day for applying to the first Digital Innovation Hubs Champions... All followers	Marta Palau...	9/23/2019	16	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
Don't miss the opportunity to participate in the first Digital Innovation Hubs Champio... All followers	Marta Palau...	9/17/2019	8	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
Don't miss the opportunity to participate in the first Digital Innovation Hubs Champio... All followers	Marta Palau...	9/14/2019	5	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
Last week for applying to the first Digital Innovation Hubs Champions Challenge! All followers	Marta Palau...	9/12/2019	5	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
How Digital Innovation Hubs #DIHs can boost productivity of #SMEs ? How... All followers	Marta Palau...	9/6/2019	11	-	0	0%	1	0	1	
Open calls TRINITY DIH Tampere Universities All followers	Marta Palau...	8/28/2019	48	-	3	6.25%	1	0	1	
Why Small and Medium enterprises should care about electronic identification (eID),... All followers	Marta Palau...	8/27/2019	28	-	1	3.57%	0	0	2	
Take a look to #L4MS #H2020 call to develop new logistics solutions. This call i... All followers	Marta Palau...	8/26/2019	20	-	1	5%	0	0	0	
DIHNET Community All followers	Marta Palau...	8/24/2019	9	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
AIOTI – Working on a network of DIHs in IOT All followers	Marta Palau...	8/23/2019	21	-	0	0%	0	0	2	
DIHs Champions Challenge All followers	Marta Palau...	8/22/2019	15	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
DIH-HERO network in #Healthcare #Robotics is funding cross-border travelli... All followers	Marta Palau...	8/20/2019	11	-	0	0%	0	0	3	
TRINITY DIH Open Call is About to be Launched! RODIN All followers	Marta Palau...	8/16/2019	16	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
DIH³ open call for Manufacturing SMEs, Mid-Caps and Technology Providers to... All followers	Marta Palau...	8/15/2019	9	-	0	0%	0	0	0	
Have your say on the future of investment in Europe's digital economy - Digital Singl... All followers	Marta Palau...	8/13/2019	9	-	0	0%	0	0	0	

Cybersecurity for Robotics 2019 Conference - CSFR2019 - Call for Papers All followers	Marta Palau...	8/12/2019	44	-	0	0%	0	0	1
Seventh meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs: the key role of... All followers	Marta Palau...	8/7/2019	34	-	0	0%	0	0	0
Web Link All followers	Marta Palau...	7/31/2019	33	-	0	0%	1	0	0

Figure 26: DIHNET LinkedIn Unique Impressions period 31 March 2019 – 13 Oct 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 13, 2019])

The engagement rate of users with the DIHNET LinkedIn page has increased since July 2019 (see Figure 27), and we expect it to keep increasing when more content is published and shared among followers and LinkedIn users. LinkedIn is a good platform for targeting a specialised audience, however more work needs to be done to build a LinkedIn DIHNET community.

Figure 27: DIHNET LinkedIn engagement rate period 31 March 2019 – 13 Oct 2019 (Source: www.twitter.com/DihnetE [Accessed October 13, 2019])

3.11 Community platform

The DIHNET community platform was officially launched on the 3rd April 2019 during the 6th Working Group meeting of DIHs. As per 27 September 2019, the **number of registered users is 331** (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: DIHNET Community members March– September 2019 (Source: Funding Box) [Accessed September 27, 2019]

The community is composed of 5 public spaces and 4 private spaces:

Public spaces	Private spaces
	<i>The private spaces were created for the Working Groups of the project to have a specific online space to interact.</i>
News & Events: Allows members to share their latest news and events.	WG1 Funding & finance (coordinated by FundinBox): Exploration of new funding sources to establish cooperation among DIHs and to facilitate the uptake of digital innovations by SMEs.
Q&A: Allows members to share their doubts and get answers from their peers.	WG2 Collaboration (coordinated by EU Robotics): Effective and sustainable collaboration at all levels (internal, regional, national and EU-wide) with special attention to cross-border collaboration and tools.
DIH Champions Challenge: This space was specifically created for the Champions Challenge that was launched in July. It allows members to ask information about the Open Call.	WG3 National and regional policies (coordinated by TECNALIA): Coherent and continuous connection to the regional, national policies and strategies to digitalise industry.
Introduce Yourself: Allows members to share who they are, and the topics that they would like to talk about in the DIHNET.EU Community.	WG4 Business models & sustainability (coordinated by BLUMORPHO): Business models for DIHs (how to structure services, possible legal forms, partners recruiting, etc.), but also on sustainability.
Criteria to be part of DIHs catalogue: Allows members to share their vision on what should be the criteria of the EC to include DIHs in the catalogue of DIHs created by the JRC.	

One of the highlights in the spaces was the Q&A session about how to update DIHs profile in the JRC catalogue and the criteria to be part of the catalogue, with more than 30 members interacting during 1 hour on the chat with Begoña Sánchez (TECNALIA) and María Roca (FBA). This session took place on the public space “Criteria to be part of DIHs catalogue”.

The community also includes 6 collections that refer to the type of content that is posted:

- **Articles:** Allows members to post articles about the topic of their choice, including images and graphs.
- **Questions:** Allows member to post questions and get answers from other members.
- **Announcements:** Allows member to post short announcements, such as the launch of an Open Call or important news.
- **Events:** Allows members to share their events (include calendar and location field).
- **DIH-related initiatives & projects:** Repository of initiatives and projects ongoing that are dealing with DIHs and their approach.
- **Ecosystem:** Repository of articles about use cases, best practices, profiles and interviews of stakeholders in the Digital Innovation Hubs ecosystem. Each month, a “DIH of the month” is posted there, with a presentation of mature DIH that can be an inspiration for others.

Since the creation of the community on the 3rd April 2019 until the 27th September 2019 there have been **165 posts**. Out of these 165 posts, we have noted 74 comments and 100 emoji reactions, which is a quite high level of member engagement.

The most successful collection is the “events” collection, with 22 events shared by members since April 2019. Accordingly, the space with the most content is “News & Events” as shown in Figure 29 below.

Figure 29: DIHNET Community messages February 2019– September 2019 (Source: Funding Box) [Accessed September 27, 2019]

3.12 Website

The DIHNET.EU project website is continuously being updated, as new information is added. The DIHNET community platform is active for people to register and participate in different webinars and discussions within the DIHNET Working Groups.

Although the DIHNET website was online since the first months of the start of the project, the google analytics of the website were not activated until 1st October 2019. The analytics shown in this section 3.12 cover only the **period from the 1st October 2019 to the 17th October 2019**. Thus, this two-week data is not significant, and should be seen only as an indicator of the current state of the website.

Figure 30: DIHNET website landing page (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

The audience overview of DIHNET website for the before mentioned period is of **223 new users** of which an **80.1%** are **new visitors** to the site (see Figure 31).

A **48.72%** of the **new users access directly the website**, while others are referred to it from external sources. This is the case of the JRC DIH catalogue website which brings a 17.09% of new users, and the European commission's website with a 8.55% of the total traffic (see Figure 31).

The percentage of referrals to the DIHNET website are shown in Figure 32, being **48.19% of referrals by the JRC DIH catalogue**.

Figure 31: DIHNET website audience overview 1 October 2019 - 17 October 2019 (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

Figure 32: DIHNET website traffic by referrals, 1 October 2019 - 17 October 2019 (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

Further to **(social) network referrals** during the period 1-17 October 2019, they are all from **Twitter** as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: DIHNET website network referrals by social network, 1 October 2019 - 17 October 2019 (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

The number of page views during the period 1-17 October 2019 is **344** of which **290** are **unique page views**.

Figure 34: DIHNET website overview 1 October 2019 - 17 October 2019 (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

The **primary countries** of the DIHNET website users (**223 users**) in period 1-17 October 2019 are **Spain (39 users)** and **USA (28 users)** as show in Figure 35. Followed by Belgium (19 users), Italy (18 users) and The Netherlands (15 users). The location data is gathered during the access to the website, so it can be either the users' country of residence or country they are temporary visiting. Most of the users are from European countries (see Figure 36), which is the geographical area of our targeted audience.

Figure 35: DIHNET website users' location by country, 1 - 17 October 2019 (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

Figure 36: DIHNET website users' location by continent, 1 - 17 October 2019 (Source: DIHNET) [Accessed October 17, 2019]

4 Dissemination materials

- **Leaflets**

euRobotics (ER) has created a series of information leaflets about the project, the working groups and the community platform. This dissemination materials are available for partners to print and distribute in different events (i.e. conferences, working group meetings, workshops, exhibitions, fairs, etc.)

An example of these materials can be found in Annex 2 of this deliverable.

- **Signature banner**

TNO designed a signature banner for consortium partners to use in the e-mail signatures. This banner allows partners to promote DIHNET through their contacts. The signature banner is show in Figure 37 below.

Figure 37: DIHNET e-mail signature banner (Source: TNO)

5 Conclusions

In this first year, all consortium partners have collaborated in disseminating the project through the organisation of different outreach activities (addressed to a specialised audience) and the publication of non-scientific articles in the trade press. DIHNET partners have also been invited to present DIHNET network in conferences and workshops; and asked to co-organise with the European Commission the successful 7th Working Group meeting on DIHs.

The success of the DIHNET community platform within the Digital Innovation Hubs community is shown by the level of registrations (331 users) and users' engagement in the webinars and working groups.

The social media evaluation shows high engagement rates in Twitter, in contrast with the need to increase the audience in the LinkedIn and Facebook pages. For a more efficient use of the personnel resources and better target our specialist audience, we will focus on LinkedIn and Twitter channels in Year 2 and pause the Facebook page. We expect this strategy to help us boost the reach and level of engagement with our targeted audience and, therefore, help to build quicker the DIHNET network community.

The overall project dissemination for this Year 1 is good. Building a community is a process that takes time and effort over several years. The first stones for building the DIHNET community have been well set and the community is growing in the right direction, as indicated by the increasing interest in our network. An interest we expect will keep growing when planned strategic efforts are put in place to nurture the community during the second year of the project.

Annexes

Annex 1

Annex 1 provides a summary of on-line media coverage of DIHNET network from the period of 1st November 2018 to the 28th October 2019.

Table 1: Online media Period November 2018 – October 2019

Num	Website	Language/ Country	Media type	Genre	Title	Date	Link
April 2019							
1	Baltic Tech Park	Lithuanian/ Lithuania	Trade	DIH	Baltijos SIC pristatytas Skaitmeninių inovacijų centrų Darbo grupės posėdyje Briuselyje	11/04/2019	https://www.baltictechpark.com/2019/04/11/baltijos-sic-pristatytas-skaitmeniniu-inovaciju-centru-darbo-grupes-posedyje-briuselyje/
2	European Commission – Smart Specialisation Platform	English/EU	Trade	Smart Specialisation	Join the DIHNET.EU Community	23/04/2019	https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/-/launch-of-the-dihnet-eu-community?inheritRedirect=true
3	Medium	English/EU	Trade	Technology	MADE as a DIH — Digital Innovation Hub	24/04/2019	https://medium.com/@i4ms_eu/made-as-a-dih-digital-innovation-hub-e18d983bb922
June 2019							
4	APTE Asociación de Parques Científicos y	Spanish/ Spain	Trade	Innovation & Technology	Los parques científicos y tecnológicos españoles participan en el 28% de	20/05/2019	https://www.apte.org/parques-cientificos-tecnologicos-participan-28-digital-innovation-hubs

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 825640.
www.dihnet.eu

D1.4 Report Year 1 Dissemination and Communication

	Tecnológicos de España				los Digital Innovation Hubs		
July 2019							
5	EU monitor	English/EU	Trade	EC	Seventh meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs, Brussels	01/07/2019	https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vkxaxdzhs1?ctx=vg9ibb65quyr
6	Smart Agri hubs	English/EU	Trade	DIH	Launch of the DIHs Champions Challenge!	18/07/2019	https://smartagrihubs.eu/latest-news/DIHNETCHALLENGE
August 2019							
7	Enterprise europe network	German/Germany	Trade	Technology & Innovation	EU-Förderung aus dem Bereich IKT	21/08/2019	https://een-thuringen.eu/news-medien/artikel/352250ee5b235301e081fdaa12639bc3.html?tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=1169&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail
8	CEEI Alcoy Valencia	Spanish/Spain	Trade	Technology & Innovation	Call DIHs Champion Challenge 2019	27/08/2019	http://ceeialcoi.emprenemjunts.es/?op=8&n=19541&lang=3
October 2019							
9	Planetic	Spanish/Spain	Trade	Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)	Jornada Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) - VI Asamblea General	10/10/2019	https://www.planetic.es/content/jornada-digital-innovation-hubs-dih-s-vi-asamblea-general

D1.4 Report Year 1 Dissemination and Communication

10	Centic	Spanish/ Spain	Trade	Innovation & Technology	Asistimos a la Jornada DIH dentro de la Asamblea de la Plataforma Planetic en Palma de Mallorca	16/10/2019	http://centic.es/noticias-tic/
Unknown date							
11	FFG The Austrian Research Promotion agency	German/ Austria	Trade	Innovation & Technology	DIH: Pan-European network of Digital Innovation Hubs	Unknown	https://www.ffg.at/europa/dih
12	BDV Big Data Value Association	English/EU	Trade	Big Data	DIHNET.EU: supporting the collaboration among Digital Innovation Hub Networks across Europe	Unknown	http://www.bdva.eu/node/1323
13	Ideal-Ist	English/EU	Trade	Information and Communication Technologies	Seventh meeting of the Working Group on Digital Innovation Hubs	Unknown	https://www.ideal-ist.eu/event/seventh-meeting-working-group-digital-innovation-hubs

Annex 2

The following dissemination materials are available for partners to print and distribute in different events. They include:

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www.dihnet.eu

Digital Innovation Hub Networks

The DIHNET.EU project enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The project aims to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

The DIHNET.EU project supports these networks and initiatives by establishing a coordination mechanism, creating synergies and addressing common issues.

More specifically, it contributes to:

- Enhance the collaboration between the different stakeholders from the European DIH Community with a wide range of services, information and tools that will help DIHs to communicate, align, collaborate and synchronize activities.
- Develop a clear overview of the DIHs related services provided in Europe and align them.
- Upgrade the DIH Catalogue by identifying/triggering activities in the DIH Community in coherence with regional, national and EU policies.
- Create a strategy to reinforce the specialisation of these services, as well as supporting its uptake by relevant DIHs and DIH networks.
- Create a vision and strategy on a self-sustaining business model for this network of DIHs, and to make this operational.
- Create an online community to foster interaction among hubs, information exchange and peer-learning.

Business models to create sustainable collaboration

European collaboration between technology oriented and local DIHs will develop and bring full growth potential if all stakeholders take benefits and generate value from it. In this respect, the efficiency of business models generating a specific European added-value out of this pan-European collaboration is key.

The objective is to identify, develop and promote the diversity of new business models that foster knowledge sharing and technologies transfer between European DIHs while enabling the sustainable development of new business opportunities for them all.

DIHNET.EU reinforces smart specialization by stimulating cross-fertilization between technology oriented and sectorial DIHs.

DIHs and Specialisation

Collaboration among Competence Centres, Digital Innovation Hubs, regional and European Initiatives is crucial in order to offer the best possible support for SMEs and Midcaps.

The DIHNET.EU project will support stakeholders in developing specialisation strategies that will help their clients and partners to develop a portfolio of services based on regional assets and comparative advantages.

DIH concept and evolution

The concepts and practice of DIHs and networks of hubs have evolved from the Competence Centres, being the core mechanisms to support digitisation, to the creation of structures where different public and private stakeholders work together to support SMEs as a Digital Innovation Hub.

Also, the growth of Regional DIHs networks working as a cross sectoral and multi-technology one-stop-shop for SMEs, supported at the same time at National and European level, show the need of moving towards a pan-European network of DIHs where DIHs offer the best possible support for SMEs and midcaps everywhere in Europe regardless of the technological domain and removing any constraints linked to regional capacities.

Within this framework, DIHNET.EU will facilitate the creation of a pan-European network of DIHs to foster the cooperation between regions offering tools to move from the traditional regional approach, to a network of DIHs acting as a doorway of European capacities to boost SMEs competitiveness.

Catalogue of DIHs

The European catalogue of DIHs, created by the Joint Research Centre (JRC), is an online repository which contains comprehensive information on digital innovation hubs across Europe. This tool aims at helping companies get access to competences needed in order to digitize their products and services.

DIHNET.EU will contribute to upgrade and update the information included in the catalogue of DIHs.

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DIHNET.EU online Community

DIHNET.EU Community is a collaboration platform that offers DIH networks, DIHs and other key stakeholders a way to interact and look for opportunities among DIHs in Europe; such as participation in projects, joint offers to DIHs, discussion on the selection criteria of DIHs, etc.

WHAT CAN BE FOUND IN THE DIHNET.EU COMMUNITY?

- **Articles:** news, interviews and conclusions related to the DIHs ecosystem.
- **Announcements:** important information for the members of the community.
- **Questions:** this section gather all the questions posed in the community by any member.
- **Events:** announce events of interest for DIHs and the opportunity to meet people that is attending.
- **Showcase:** collection of information listing all EU initiatives supporting DIHs.
- **Real-time chats:** conversation spaces to foster 1:1 interaction.

WHAT DOES THE DIHNET.EU COMMUNITY OFFER?

- Access to **training** (webinars) on community building, business models and more.
- **Guidance & Support** to take advantage of the DIHNET.EU community.
- Become one of the **featured initiatives supporting** DIHs and gain visibility.
- Invite other **DIHs to join your network** and offer them your services.

- Become an **active member** of the DIHNET.EU community by sharing articles and information related to your project activities (newsletters, events).
- Get first-hand and fresh **collaboration opportunities to offer to the DIHs** in your network.
- Create a **private space** within the DIHNET.EU platform for your internal communications and ensure your DIHs are represented in the DIHNET.EU community.

- Invite your DIHs to **participate in the working groups** & decide on the future of DIHs.

- **Take part/benefit from DIHNET online & offline events** and offer them to the DIHs within your network. Events such as Q&A, international events, follow-up on the DIHs Working Groups of the EC and many more.

We will be happy to **guide you through the community features** and **get your network to the next level!**

For more information on [DIHNET.EU](https://www.dihnet.eu) online community, contact:

Maria Roca
[@mariaroca](https://twitter.com/mariaroca) (Spaces Funding Box)
maria.roca@fundingbox.com

Join the
 DIHNET.EU
 online
 Community

Working Group Finance and Funding opportunities

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and Funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The Working Group on Finance and Funding opportunities focuses on exploring new funding sources that contribute to establishing cooperation among DIHs. This group works on new strategies to raise interest from private investors, banks and corporates and looks for synergies with national and regional funding schemes. It also contributes to identify different funding sources and opportunities to facilitate the uptake of digital innovations by SMEs.

What are the challenges?

- Attracting private investments.
- Finding EU funding opportunities (H2020 & Horizon Europe) to enhance cooperation among DIHs.
- Accessing to best practices.
- Discovering synergies among different funding schemes & link to Smart Specialisation Strategies.
- Linking funding instruments to policy implementation.
- Funding DIHs collaboration (other than H2020).
- Financing DIH's operations.

How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

Graciela Garrido
“Finance & Funding opportunities” WG Coordinator
graciela.garrido@fundingbox.com

Join the
DIHNET.EU
online
Community!

Working Group Collaboration activities and mechanisms

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The objective of the Working Group on “Collaboration activities and mechanisms” is to address the challenges and barriers to improve DIHs collaboration; and to understand and exchange good practices that can feed the learning process. This WG focuses on cross-border collaboration as well as on the mechanisms and tools needed to ensure effective and sustainable cooperation.

What are the challenges?

- Linking the existing individual DIH structures, projects, initiatives, national and regional hubs, etc.
- Building a pan-European network of DIHs.
- Identifying and reaching the end-users of the DIHs.
- Identifying the tools needed and jointly develop them.

How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

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Working Group Connection with policies and strategies

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and Funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The Working Group on “Connection with policies and strategies” focuses on exploring the challenges and actions needed to ensure alignment and coherence of DIHs to the regional, national and EU policies and strategies to digitalise industry, especially to Smart Specialisation.

What are the challenges?

- Strategies at regional, national and EU level supporting DIH collaboration.
- Mechanisms in place to support cross-border/interregional/national cooperation and technology transfer.
- Contribution of DIHs in shaping regional/national/EU digital transformation strategies.
- Involvement of DIHs for the implementation of these strategies.
- Identification of Best Practices.
- Ensuring DIH connection and alignment to the strategies.

Being part of a regional, national or European policy initiative to digitise the industry is one of the criteria for a DIH to be part of the Catalogue. How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

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Working Group Business Models & Sustainability

DIHNET.EU aims at developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), DIH networks and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The DIHNET Working Groups (WG) will identify and target challenges that require the input from the DIH community and the different stakeholders in four main topics: “Finance and funding opportunities”, “Collaboration activities and mechanisms”, “Connection with policies and strategies” and “Business Models and Sustainability”.

Objectives

The objective of the Working Group on “Business Models and Sustainability” is to address the challenges to ensure effective and sustainable collaboration among the DIHs in Europe and explore possibilities for business models that can support this collaboration and effective network.

Special attention will be paid to identify the possible constraints and obstacles in the setting-up of European collaboration between DIHs and to define relevant actions to overcome such challenges.

What are the challenges?

- To identify the prerequisites of successful pan-European collaborations.
- To identify the added value of collaborating and participating in a network (why is a pan-European network important and needed)
- To identify possible business models for collaboration in a network.
- To jointly develop a common understanding and plan for future participation and development in pan-EU collaboration activities.

How the DIH community is going to address these challenges will be discussed in the working group.

How to get engaged with the WG

You can join the DIHNET.EU Community platform at www.dihnet.eu or contact the WG coordinator.

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